

Supplementary Information 3

Table SI.3.1. Membership information for six trophic role groups derived from REGE analysis.

Food web name	Group ID	Group Member ID
Bar	Group 1	38, 38.1, 38.2, 37, 39, 40, 41
	Group 2	3, 9, 9.1, 7, 1, 1.1, 1.2
	Group 3	32, 20, 11, 8, 8.1, 8.2, 8.3, 18, 18.1, 8.4, 8.5, 8.6, 8.7, 8.8, 10, 8.9, 16, 6, 13, 8.1, 2, 2.1, 2.2, 30, 30.1, 28, 28.1, 30.2, 22, 33, 27, 35
	Group 4	29, 29.1, 34, 34.1, 31, 36
	Group 5	23, 21, 21.1, 21.2, 23.1, 21.3, 23.2, 23.3, 21.4, 17, 5, 15, 19, 25, 23.4, 23.5, 23.6, 24, 26
	Group 6	4, 4.1, 4.2, 14, 14.1, 14.2, 12, 12.1
Pws	Group 1	6, 6.1, 23, 5, 5.1, 14, 14.1, 14.2, 14.3, 14.4, 14.5, 14.6, 14.7, 14.8, 14.9, 11, 8, 9, 12, 4, 10
	Group 2	29, 29.1, 29.2, 29.3, 29.4
	Group 3	18, 1, 2, 13, 13.1
	Group 4	44, 43, 44.1, 45, 45.1, 45.2, 45.3, 45.4, 46, 47, 48
	Group 5	33, 36, 33.1, 36.1, 33.2, 36.2, 20, 16, 20.1, 20.2, 7, 17, 15, 15.1, 15.2, 15.3, 3, 3.1, 3.2, 33.3, 36.3, 33.4, 36.4, 24, 24.1, 39, 39.1, 21, 33.5, 36.5, 39.2, 33.6, 36.6, 37
	Group 6	34, 35, 30, 27, 22, 25, 26, 31, 28, 28.1, 28.2, 41, 42, 34.1, 35.1, 34.2, 35.2, 34.3, 35.3, 34.4, 35.4, 41.1, 42.1, 41.2, 42.2, 41.3, 42.3, 41.4, 42.4, 41.5, 42.5, 38, 40, 38.1, 32, 19
Chs	Group 1	25, 25.1, 25.2, 25.3, 25.4, 25.5, 41
	Group 2	43, 42, 44, 45
	Group 3	18, 20, 22, 11, 12, 13, 13.1, 13.2, 30, 34, 35, 32, 38, 39, 40
	Group 4	36, 24, 24.1, 23, 24.2, 24.3, 24.4, 23.1, 24.5, 24.6, 24.7, 24.8, 4, 23.2, 23.3, 16, 17, 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 21, 10, 21.1, 23.4, 15, 15.1, 15.2, 15.3, 15.4, 14, 27, 27.1, 31
	Group 5	28, 28.1, 28.2, 5, 3, 26, 37
	Group 6	29, 29.1, 29.2, 9, 19, 19.1, 33
Car	Group 1	14
	Group 2	70, 71
	Group 3	74, 83, 75, 54, 69, 82, 81, 55, 58, 44, 51, 65, 64, 63, 59, 61, 62, 57, 45, 66, 60, 79, 77, 53, 80, 76, 78, 67, 68, 42

Group 4 38, 39, 41, 52, 48, 50, 49, 40, 23, 72, 24, 47, 43, 73, 56,
46

Group 5 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8

Group 6 11, 19, 15, 18, 20, 22, 21, 16, 29, 30, 32, 31, 17, 25, 26,
27, 28, 35, 33, 34, 37, 36, 13, 10, 12, 9

Gad

Group 1 70, 72, 76, 80, 83, 69, 79, 64, 89, 67, 77, 78

Group 2 34, 37, 36, 35, 38, 39, 42, 46, 40, 45, 44, 43, 41

Group 3 85, 74, 75, 68, 47, 52, 57, 58, 62, 61, 48, 63, 60, 55, 54,
53, 56, 59, 71, 66, 81, 82, 84, 86, 88, 65, 87, 1, 13, 33, 73

Group 4 16, 15, 21, 31, 29, 26, 25, 28, 30, 24

Group 5 95, 11, 96, 17, 93, 90

Group 6 14, 12, 94, 51, 3, 2, 49, 50, 22, 91, 19, 5, 4, 23, 20, 6, 7,
10, 27, 8, 9, 32, 18, 92

Table SI.3.2. Membership information for six trophic role groups derived from TSM analysis.

Food web name	Group ID	Group Member ID
Bar	Group 1	32, 17, 19, 25, 26, 29, 29.1, 30, 30.1, 28, 28.1, 30.2, 31
	Group 2	20, 4, 4.1, 4.2, 11, 18, 18.1, 14, 14.1, 14.2, 5, 10, 15, 16, 13, 12, 12.1, 34, 34.1, 33, 38, 38.1, 38.2, 35, 36, 37, 39, 40, 41
	Group 3	3, 9, 9.1, 7, 1, 1.1, 1.2
	Group 4	23, 23.1, 23.2, 23.3, 23.4, 23.5, 23.6, 24
	Group 5	8, 8.1, 8.2, 8.3, 8.4, 8.5, 8.6, 8.7, 8.8, 8.9, 6, 8.1, 2, 2.1, 2.2
	Group 6	21, 21.1, 21.2, 21.3, 21.4, 22, 27
Pws	Group 1	44, 43, 44.1, 45, 6, 6.1, 23, 18, 5, 5.1, 1, 2, 29, 29.1, 29.2, 29.3, 29.4, 13, 13.1, 30, 20, 16, 27, 11, 20.1, 8, 20.2, 7, 17, 22, 25, 9, 12, 4, 15, 15.1, 10, 26, 31, 15.2, 15.3, 3, 3.1, 3.2, 28, 28.1, 28.2, 41, 24, 24.1, 41.1, 41.2, 41.3, 39, 39.1, 21, 41.4, 41.5, 38, 40, 38.1, 39.2, 32, 45.1, 45.2, 45.3, 45.4, 19, 37, 46, 47, 48
	Group 2	34, 35, 34.1, 35.1, 34.2, 35.2, 34.3, 35.3, 34.4, 35.4
	Group 3	33, 33.1, 33.2, 33.3, 33.4, 33.5, 33.6
	Group 4	36, 36.1, 36.2, 36.3, 36.4, 36.5, 36.6
	Group 5	14, 14.1, 14.2, 14.3, 14.4, 14.5, 14.6, 14.7, 14.8, 14.9
	Group 6	42, 42.1, 42.2, 42.3, 42.4, 42.5
Chs	Group 1	43, 36, 28, 28.1, 28.2, 4, 5, 16, 17, 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 18, 8, 10, 20, 22, 11, 12, 13, 13.1, 13.2, 14, 27, 26, 27.1, 30, 31, 34, 35, 32, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 44, 45
	Group 2	29, 29.1, 29.2, 9, 19, 19.1, 33
	Group 3	24, 24.1, 24.2, 24.3, 24.4, 24.5, 24.6, 24.7, 24.8
	Group 4	25, 25.1, 25.2, 25.3, 25.4, 25.5
	Group 5	23, 23.1, 23.2, 23.3, 23.4
	Group 6	21, 21.1, 15, 15.1, 15.2, 15.3, 15.4
Car	Group 1	38, 39, 70, 71, 14, 41, 52, 48, 50, 49, 42, 40, 23, 72, 24, 47, 43, 73, 19, 56, 46, 32, 27, 28, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8
	Group 2	11, 15, 18, 20, 16, 29, 30, 31, 17, 25, 26, 13, 10, 12, 9
	Group 3	74, 83, 75, 69, 81, 65, 64, 63, 59, 61, 66, 60, 77, 78, 67, 68
	Group 4	54, 82, 51, 79, 53, 80, 76
	Group 5	55, 58, 44, 62, 57, 45
	Group 6	22, 21, 35, 33, 34, 37, 36

Gad	Group 1	85, 74, 75, 68, 47, 52, 57, 58, 62, 61, 63, 60, 55, 54, 53, 56, 59, 71, 66, 81, 82, 84, 86, 88, 65, 87, 73
	Group 2	70, 72, 76, 80, 83, 69, 79, 64, 89, 67, 77, 78
	Group 3	16, 14, 21, 31, 29, 26, 25, 28, 30, 24
	Group 4	15, 95, 11, 12, 96, 94, 51, 2, 49, 50, 17, 22, 91, 19, 23, 20, 34, 93, 27, 32, 90, 48, 18, 92, 1, 13, 33
	Group 5	3, 5, 4, 6, 7, 10, 8, 9
	Group 6	37, 36, 35, 38, 39, 42, 46, 40, 45, 44, 43, 41

Table SI.3.3. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage using various numbers of trophic role groups for Barents Sea food web.

Number of clusters	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
3	1	65(3)	5.90	6.27	0.09	0.001
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.25	0.73	0.007
	3	7(4)	2.67	6.31	0.72	0.001
4	1	32(2)	5.86	6.26	0.26	0.060
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.26	0.76	0.004
	3	33(1)	5.84	6.26	0.24	0.045
	4	7(4)	2.67	6.29	0.74	0.001
5	1	32(2)	5.86	6.28	0.24	0.045
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.32	0.71	0.001
	3	27(0)	5.20	6.26	0.28	0.001
	4	6(1)	4.80	6.27	0.78	0.035
	5	7(4)	2.67	6.24	0.78	0.001
6	1	32(2)	5.86	6.26	0.25	0.061
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.28	0.76	0.005
	3	8(0)	5.54	6.25	0.65	0.140
	4	19(0)	4.58	6.27	0.38	0.001
	5	6(1)	4.80	6.26	0.78	0.045
	6	7(4)	2.67	6.31	0.72	0.001
7	1	10(2)	4.04	6.28	0.59	0.001
	2	22(0)	5.20	6.28	0.35	0.003
	3	7(0)	4.10	6.28	0.74	0.004
	4	8(0)	5.54	6.30	0.67	0.139
	5	19(0)	4.58	6.26	0.37	0.001
	6	6(1)	4.80	6.27	0.82	0.044
	7	7(4)	2.67	6.23	0.73	0.001
8	1	10(2)	4.04	6.30	0.57	0.001
	2	22(0)	5.20	6.26	0.33	0.002
	3	7(0)	4.10	6.28	0.72	0.003
	4	6(0)	5.53	6.27	0.83	0.179
	5	19(0)	4.58	6.26	0.37	0.001
	6	2(0)	2.00	6.31	1.72	0.013
	7	6(1)	4.80	6.28	0.81	0.044
	8	7(4)	2.67	6.28	0.78	0.001
9	1	10(2)	4.04	6.29	0.58	0.002

10

2	22(0)	5.20	6.27	0.32	0.002
3	7(0)	4.10	6.21	0.73	0.003
4	6(0)	5.53	6.31	0.82	0.158
5	19(0)	4.58	6.27	0.37	0.001
6	2(0)	2.00	6.29	1.80	0.014
7	6(1)	4.80	6.21	0.81	0.049
8	3(0)	2.67	6.28	1.37	0.009
9	4(4)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
1	10(2)	4.04	6.26	0.59	0.001
2	22(0)	5.20	6.26	0.34	0.001
3	7(0)	4.10	6.30	0.74	0.004
4	6(0)	5.53	6.27	0.83	0.171
5	17(0)	4.49	6.27	0.41	0.001
6	2(0)	3.00	6.30	1.83	0.052
7	2(0)	2.00	6.27	1.75	0.020
8	6(1)	4.80	6.26	0.81	0.054
9	3(0)	2.67	6.30	1.43	0.011
10	4(4)	0.00	NA	NA	NA

Table SI.3.4. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage using various numbers of trophic role groups for Prince William Sound food web.

Number of clusters	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value	
3	1	11(3)	3.46	6.57	0.54	0.001	
	2	70(2)	6.16	6.56	0.13	0.003	
	3	31(0)	5.69	6.56	0.28	0.003	
4	1	11(3)	3.46	6.56	0.53	0.001	
	2	36(1)	6.38	6.56	0.25	0.245	
	3	34(1)	5.62	6.56	0.26	0.001	
4	4	31(0)	5.69	6.57	0.28	0.002	
	5	1	11(3)	3.46	6.59	0.55	0.001
	2	36(1)	6.38	6.56	0.24	0.225	
5	3	34(1)	5.62	6.55	0.26	0.002	
	4	21(0)	5.98	6.56	0.36	0.067	
	5	10(0)	4.27	6.58	0.56	0.001	
6	1	11(3)	3.46	6.57	0.54	0.001	
	2	36(1)	6.38	6.55	0.24	0.234	
	3	34(1)	5.62	6.56	0.26	0.002	
	4	21(0)	5.98	6.57	0.37	0.067	
	5	5(0)	3.60	6.61	0.90	0.002	
	6	5(0)	2.60	6.55	0.88	0.001	
7	1	11(3)	3.46	6.58	0.51	0.001	
	2	24(1)	6.06	6.59	0.33	0.052	
	3	34(1)	5.62	6.55	0.24	0.001	
	4	21(0)	5.98	6.54	0.35	0.062	
	5	5(0)	3.60	6.57	0.91	0.003	
	6	5(0)	2.60	6.59	0.85	0.001	
	7	12(0)	5.33	6.54	0.53	0.012	
8	1	11(3)	3.46	6.56	0.54	0.001	
	2	24(1)	6.06	6.57	0.34	0.061	
	3	24(1)	5.73	6.57	0.34	0.010	
	4	10(0)	4.73	6.57	0.57	0.002	
	5	21(0)	5.98	6.56	0.35	0.062	
	6	5(0)	3.60	6.59	0.88	0.001	
	7	5(0)	2.60	6.51	0.93	0.001	
	8	12(0)	5.33	6.55	0.50	0.008	
9	1	11(3)	3.46	6.59	0.55	0.001	

10

2	21(1)	5.77	6.57	0.37	0.021
3	24(1)	5.73	6.58	0.34	0.008
4	10(0)	4.73	6.54	0.59	0.003
5	21(0)	5.98	6.55	0.37	0.068
6	5(0)	3.60	6.58	0.89	0.001
7	5(0)	2.60	6.54	0.89	0.001
8	3(0)	2.67	6.58	1.28	0.002
9	12(0)	5.33	6.56	0.50	0.010
1	2(0)	2.00	6.47	1.75	0.012
2	9(3)	3.67	6.56	0.62	0.001
3	21(1)	5.77	6.56	0.36	0.018
4	24(1)	5.73	6.57	0.33	0.009
5	10(0)	4.73	6.57	0.57	0.001
6	21(0)	5.98	6.56	0.36	0.052
7	5(0)	3.60	6.52	0.91	0.001
8	5(0)	2.60	6.57	0.91	0.001
9	3(0)	2.67	6.60	1.27	0.003
10	12(0)	5.33	6.57	0.51	0.010

Table SI.3.5. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage using various numbers of trophic role groups for Chesapeake Bay food web.

Number of clusters	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
3	1	26(7)	5.22	5.09	0.26	0.309
	2	35(0)	4.26	5.09	0.20	0.001
	3	14(0)	5.68	5.07	0.39	0.054
4	1	19(6)	5.05	5.10	0.33	0.443
	2	35(0)	4.26	5.08	0.20	0.001
	3	14(0)	5.68	5.09	0.40	0.066
	4	7(1)	4.00	5.07	0.63	0.058
5	1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	2	35(0)	4.26	5.08	0.19	0.001
	3	14(0)	5.68	5.09	0.41	0.075
	4	7(1)	4.00	5.09	0.64	0.047
	5	15(3)	4.89	5.09	0.37	0.295
6	1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	2	35(0)	4.26	5.09	0.20	0.001
	3	7(0)	4.67	5.08	0.62	0.250
	4	7(0)	6.48	5.08	0.62	0.009
	5	7(1)	4.00	5.12	0.62	0.042
	6	15(3)	4.89	5.07	0.39	0.320
7	1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	2	8(0)	4.32	5.08	0.59	0.092
	3	7(0)	4.67	5.08	0.62	0.254
	4	7(0)	6.48	5.09	0.60	0.007
	5	27(0)	3.99	5.08	0.25	0.001
	6	7(1)	4.00	5.11	0.63	0.042
	7	15(3)	4.89	5.08	0.39	0.314
8	1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	2	8(0)	4.32	5.10	0.56	0.090
	3	7(0)	4.67	5.13	0.62	0.236
	4	7(0)	6.48	5.07	0.64	0.006
	5	27(0)	3.99	5.08	0.24	0.001
	6	7(1)	4.00	5.11	0.62	0.038
	7	12(1)	4.84	5.06	0.42	0.319
	8	3(2)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
9	1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA

10

2	8(0)	4.32	5.09	0.57	0.093
3	7(0)	4.67	5.15	0.63	0.217
4	7(0)	6.48	5.10	0.62	0.014
5	17(0)	3.93	5.09	0.34	0.001
6	7(1)	4.00	5.09	0.60	0.040
7	10(0)	3.84	5.09	0.50	0.008
8	12(1)	4.84	5.06	0.44	0.309
9	3(2)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
1	4(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
2	8(0)	4.32	5.07	0.57	0.096
3	7(0)	4.67	5.07	0.60	0.243
4	7(0)	6.48	5.09	0.64	0.011
5	17(0)	3.93	5.08	0.34	0.001
6	7(1)	4.00	5.10	0.63	0.047
7	10(0)	3.84	5.10	0.50	0.005
8	8(0)	3.29	5.10	0.57	0.002
9	3(2)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
10	4(1)	2.00	5.12	0.90	0.001

Table SI.3.6. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage using various numbers of trophic role groups for Carpinteria Salt Marsh food web.

Number of clusters	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
3	1	16(0)	6.09	6.72	0.40	0.064
	2	34(8)	5.55	6.74	0.22	0.001
	3	33(0)	5.41	6.73	0.22	0.001
4	1	16(0)	6.09	6.73	0.40	0.058
	2	26(0)	5.55	6.72	0.28	0.001
	3	33(0)	5.41	6.73	0.23	0.001
	4	8(8)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
5	1	16(0)	6.09	6.74	0.39	0.046
	2	26(0)	5.55	6.73	0.27	0.001
	3	32(0)	5.45	6.74	0.23	0.001
	4	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	5	8(8)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
6	1	16(0)	6.09	6.73	0.39	0.051
	2	26(0)	5.55	6.73	0.28	0.001
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.73	0.25	0.001
	4	2(0)	2.00	6.69	1.89	0.010
	5	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	6	8(8)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
7	1	16(0)	6.09	6.75	0.39	0.055
	2	24(0)	5.66	6.71	0.30	0.001
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.73	0.25	0.001
	4	2(0)	2.00	6.68	1.94	0.016
	5	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	6	2(0)	5.00	6.76	1.93	0.173
	7	8(8)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
8	1	9(0)	5.50	6.74	0.62	0.029
	2	24(0)	5.66	6.73	0.29	0.002
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.72	0.24	0.001
	4	2(0)	2.00	6.59	1.98	0.014
	5	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	6	7(0)	5.43	6.77	0.72	0.047
	7	2(0)	5.00	6.75	1.91	0.189
	8	8(8)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
9	1	9(0)	5.50	6.75	0.58	0.029

	2	24(0)	5.66	6.72	0.30	0.001
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.73	0.25	0.001
	4	2(0)	2.00	6.76	2.00	0.017
	5	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	6	7(0)	5.43	6.69	0.71	0.053
	7	2(0)	5.00	6.71	1.91	0.177
	8	3(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	9	5(5)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
10	1	5(0)	5.40	6.68	0.95	0.099
	2	24(0)	5.66	6.74	0.30	0.001
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.73	0.25	0.001
	4	4(0)	4.83	6.72	1.13	0.059
	5	2(0)	2.00	6.78	1.97	0.012
	6	1(0)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	7	7(0)	5.43	6.72	0.71	0.050
	8	2(0)	5.00	6.71	1.92	0.187
	9	3(3)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
	10	5(5)	0.00	NA	NA	NA

Table SI.3.7. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage using various numbers of trophic role groups for Grande de Gredos food web.

Number of clusters	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
3	1	44(5)	6.25	7.39	0.21	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.38	0.60	0.001
	3	40(2)	5.39	7.39	0.23	0.001
4	1	44(5)	6.25	7.39	0.22	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.40	0.57	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.40	0.64	0.001
	4	30(2)	5.57	7.38	0.30	0.001
5	1	44(5)	6.25	7.38	0.21	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.36	0.56	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.40	0.65	0.002
	4	24(2)	5.48	7.41	0.35	0.001
	5	6(0)	5.13	7.41	1.00	0.016
6	1	31(5)	6.30	7.39	0.29	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.39	0.57	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.38	0.67	0.001
	4	24(2)	5.48	7.40	0.35	0.001
	5	6(0)	5.13	7.41	0.99	0.019
	6	13(0)	4.77	7.39	0.55	0.001
7	1	31(5)	6.30	7.40	0.30	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.38	0.61	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.36	0.66	0.001
	4	12(2)	5.56	7.40	0.57	0.002
	5	6(0)	5.13	7.38	0.97	0.015
	6	12(0)	5.24	7.41	0.57	0.002
	7	13(0)	4.77	7.39	0.55	0.001
8	1	31(5)	6.30	7.38	0.27	0.001
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.39	0.55	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.42	0.65	0.001
	4	12(2)	5.56	7.42	0.57	0.001
	5	6(0)	5.13	7.41	0.99	0.018
	6	3(0)	3.33	7.35	1.93	0.036
	7	9(0)	5.06	7.39	0.70	0.002
	8	13(0)	4.77	7.38	0.53	0.001
9	1	28(3)	6.40	7.39	0.31	0.004

10

2	12(3)	4.61	7.41	0.56	0.001
3	10(0)	4.24	7.44	0.63	0.001
4	12(2)	5.56	7.37	0.59	0.004
5	6(0)	5.13	7.35	1.03	0.028
6	3(0)	3.33	7.37	1.88	0.026
7	9(0)	5.06	7.40	0.71	0.001
8	13(0)	4.77	7.39	0.52	0.001
9	3(2)	0.00	NA	NA	NA
1	28(3)	6.40	7.39	0.32	0.001
2	12(3)	4.61	7.38	0.59	0.001
3	10(0)	4.24	7.39	0.65	0.001
4	12(2)	5.56	7.37	0.60	0.009
5	4(0)	5.00	7.32	1.45	0.066
6	2(0)	7.00	7.48	2.45	0.433
7	3(0)	3.33	7.44	1.93	0.026
8	9(0)	5.06	7.44	0.70	0.001
9	13(0)	4.77	7.42	0.57	0.001
10	3(2)	0.00	NA	NA	NA

Table SI.3.8. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (REGE-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=1$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	7(4)	2.67	6.55	1.11	0.001
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.49	0.61	0.001
	3	32(2)	5.86	6.21	0.25	0.087
	4	6(1)	4.80	6.48	0.78	0.028
	5	19(0)	4.58	6.04	0.38	0.001
	6	8(0)	5.54	6.25	0.62	0.134
Pws	1	21(0)	5.98	6.59	0.33	0.031
	2	5(0)	2.6	6.54	0.80	0.001
	3	5(0)	3.6	6.46	0.85	0.002
	4	11(3)	3.46	6.50	0.61	0.001
	5	34(1)	5.62	6.46	0.25	0.001
	6	36(1)	6.38	6.60	0.24	0.174
Chs	1	7(1)	4	4.99	0.65	0.071
	2	4(3)	0	NA	NA	NA
	3	15(3)	4.89	5.16	0.36	0.228
	4	35(0)	4.26	4.98	0.19	0.001
	5	7(0)	4.67	5.11	0.55	0.205
	6	7(0)	6.48	5.39	0.56	0.022
Car	1	1(0)	0	NA	NA	NA
	2	2(0)	2	6.55	1.93	0.022
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.59	0.23	0.001
	4	16(0)	6.09	6.68	0.36	0.053
	5	8(8)	0	NA	NA	NA
	6	26(0)	5.55	6.75	0.25	0.001
Gad	1	12(3)	4.61	7.13	0.67	0.001
	2	13(0)	4.77	7.28	0.51	0.001
	3	31(5)	6.3	7.36	0.31	0.001
	4	10(0)	4.24	7.13	0.70	0.001
	5	6(0)	5.13	7.16	0.90	0.016
	6	24(2)	5.48	7.19	0.39	0.001

Table SI.3.9. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (REGE-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=2$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	7(4)	2.67	6.28	1.31	0.028
	2	7(0)	4.10	6.22	0.66	0.002
	3	32(2)	5.86	6.09	0.22	0.147
	4	6(1)	4.80	6.20	0.77	0.064
	5	19(0)	4.58	5.53	0.39	0.006
	6	8(0)	5.54	6.09	0.56	0.161
Pws	1	21(0)	5.98	6.49	0.31	0.048
	2	5(0)	2.6	5.99	0.97	0.001
	3	5(0)	3.6	5.93	0.86	0.004
	4	11(3)	3.46	6.12	0.70	0.001
	5	34(1)	5.62	6.17	0.24	0.010
	6	36(1)	6.38	6.62	0.23	0.156
Chs	1	7(1)	4	4.74	0.59	0.110
	2	4(3)	0	NA	NA	NA
	3	15(3)	4.89	5.18	0.32	0.184
	4	35(0)	4.26	4.78	0.18	0.001
	5	7(0)	4.67	5.04	0.47	0.204
	6	7(0)	6.48	5.88	0.50	0.101
Car	1	1(0)	0	NA	NA	NA
	2	2(0)	2	5.52	2.33	0.105
	3	30(0)	5.39	6.24	0.26	0.001
	4	16(0)	6.09	6.50	0.34	0.130
	5	8(8)	0	NA	NA	NA
	6	26(0)	5.55	6.44	0.27	0.001
Gad	1	12(3)	4.61	6.43	0.73	0.006
	2	13(0)	4.77	6.55	0.62	0.003
	3	31(5)	6.3	7.01	0.33	0.014
	4	10(0)	4.24	6.10	0.88	0.020
	5	6(0)	5.13	6.60	0.90	0.055
	6	24(2)	5.48	6.57	0.45	0.013

Table SI.3.10. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (REGE-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=3$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	7(4)	2.67	4.91	1.65	0.156
	2	7(0)	4.10	5.04	0.71	0.104
	3	32(2)	5.86	5.95	0.16	0.302
	4	6(1)	4.80	5.46	0.70	0.235
	5	19(0)	4.58	4.98	0.31	0.086
	6	8(0)	5.54	5.78	0.40	0.275
Pws	1	21(0)	5.98	6.21	0.23	0.160
	2	5(0)	2.6	4.29	1.17	0.096
	3	5(0)	3.6	4.80	0.84	0.062
	4	11(3)	3.46	5.01	0.72	0.016
	5	34(1)	5.62	5.86	0.18	0.085
	6	36(1)	6.38	6.50	0.17	0.241
Chs	1	7(1)	4	4.37	0.50	0.252
	2	4(3)	0	NA	NA	NA
	3	15(3)	4.89	5.08	0.25	0.215
	4	35(0)	4.26	4.50	0.14	0.039
	5	7(0)	4.67	4.85	0.34	0.307
	6	7(0)	6.48	6.25	0.32	0.244
Car	1	1(0)	0	NA	NA	NA
	2	2(0)	2	3.62	2.26	0.305
	3	30(0)	5.39	5.74	0.20	0.025
	4	16(0)	6.09	6.27	0.27	0.252
	5	8(8)	0	NA	NA	NA
	6	26(0)	5.55	5.92	0.23	0.038
Gad	1	12(3)	4.61	5.46	0.61	0.078
	2	13(0)	4.77	5.54	0.52	0.047
	3	31(5)	6.3	6.60	0.27	0.152
	4	10(0)	4.24	4.95	0.69	0.146
	5	6(0)	5.13	5.79	0.72	0.176
	6	24(2)	5.48	5.91	0.36	0.124

Table SI.3.11. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (REGE-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=4$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	7(4)	2.67	4.18	1.47	0.231
	2	7(0)	4.10	4.32	0.42	0.369
	3	32(2)	5.86	5.88	0.09	0.429
	4	6(1)	4.80	5.00	0.45	0.413
	5	19(0)	4.58	4.67	0.16	0.352
	6	8(0)	5.54	5.60	0.19	0.427
Pws	1	21(0)	5.98	6.04	0.13	0.356
	2	5(0)	2.6	3.03	0.77	0.352
	3	5(0)	3.6	3.94	0.52	0.300
	4	11(3)	3.46	4.22	0.62	0.137
	5	34(1)	5.62	5.69	0.11	0.268
	6	36(1)	6.38	6.42	0.10	0.354
Chs	1	7(1)	4	4.13	0.29	0.390
	2	4(3)	0	NA	NA	NA
	3	15(3)	4.89	4.96	0.16	0.343
	4	35(0)	4.26	4.33	0.09	0.187
	5	7(0)	4.67	4.73	0.20	0.422
	6	7(0)	6.48	6.41	0.16	0.391
Car	1	1(0)	0	NA	NA	NA
	2	2(0)	2	2.37	1.22	0.450
	3	30(0)	5.39	5.48	0.12	0.232
	4	16(0)	6.09	6.14	0.16	0.407
	5	8(8)	0	NA	NA	NA
	6	26(0)	5.55	5.64	0.14	0.296
Gad	1	12(3)	4.61	4.94	0.43	0.263
	2	13(0)	4.77	4.96	0.29	0.291
	3	31(5)	6.3	6.40	0.16	0.357
	4	10(0)	4.24	4.44	0.40	0.344
	5	6(0)	5.13	5.31	0.40	0.381
	6	24(2)	5.48	5.59	0.20	0.353

Table SI.3.12. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (TSM-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=1$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	13(0)	5.64	6.34	0.43	0.053
	2	29(6)	6.61	6.31	0.30	0.147
	3	7(0)	4.10	6.49	0.61	0.001
	4	8(0)	4.32	6.04	0.66	0.009
	5	15(0)	5.09	6.10	0.44	0.018
	6	7(1)	5.60	6.17	0.71	0.203
Pws	1	72(5)	6.61	6.57	0.13	0.397
	2	10(0)	3.38	6.47	0.54	0.001
	3	7(0)	3.81	6.30	0.70	0.001
	4	7(0)	3.81	6.27	0.74	0.001
	5	10(0)	4.09	6.65	0.53	0.001
	6	6(0)	5.87	6.68	0.75	0.135
Chs	1	41(7)	4.91	5.08	0.18	0.176
	2	7(0)	6.48	5.36	0.58	0.023
	3	9(0)	4.11	5.05	0.50	0.033
	4	6(0)	4.00	4.96	0.63	0.066
	5	5(0)	2.40	4.89	0.74	0.001
	6	7(0)	3.90	5.02	0.57	0.033
Car	1	32(8)	6.57	6.70	0.26	0.292
	2	15(0)	5.10	6.71	0.38	0.001
	3	16(0)	5.29	6.60	0.40	0.003
	4	7(0)	4.76	6.59	0.67	0.004
	5	6(0)	4.00	6.57	0.77	0.001
	6	7(0)	4.95	6.77	0.66	0.009
Gad	1	27(2)	6.40	7.36	0.33	0.002
	2	12(3)	4.61	7.11	0.68	0.001
	3	10(0)	4.24	7.08	0.75	0.001
	4	27(5)	5.82	7.28	0.38	0.001
	5	8(0)	4.71	7.09	0.85	0.009
	6	12(0)	3.92	7.21	0.57	0.001

Table SI.3.13. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (TSM-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=2$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	13(0)	5.64	6.15	0.34	0.069
	2	29(6)	6.61	6.44	0.27	0.276
	3	7(0)	4.10	6.21	0.65	0.002
	4	8(0)	4.32	5.53	0.67	0.034
	5	15(0)	5.09	5.78	0.41	0.043
	6	7(1)	5.60	5.94	0.71	0.302
Pws	1	72(5)	6.61	6.58	0.12	0.423
	2	10(0)	3.38	5.79	0.66	0.001
	3	7(0)	3.81	5.52	0.75	0.010
	4	7(0)	3.81	5.57	0.78	0.010
	5	10(0)	4.09	6.28	0.56	0.001
	6	6(0)	5.87	6.68	0.73	0.139
Chs	1	41(7)	4.91	5.02	0.16	0.238
	2	7(0)	6.48	5.89	0.50	0.105
	3	9(0)	4.11	4.91	0.48	0.049
	4	6(0)	4.00	4.77	0.64	0.124
	5	5(0)	2.40	4.38	0.78	0.003
	6	7(0)	3.90	4.84	0.54	0.040
Car	1	32(8)	6.57	6.63	0.25	0.407
	2	15(0)	5.10	6.30	0.43	0.002
	3	16(0)	5.29	6.21	0.41	0.010
	4	7(0)	4.76	6.16	0.72	0.023
	5	6(0)	4.00	5.95	0.88	0.009
	6	7(0)	4.95	6.44	0.70	0.017
Gad	1	27(2)	6.40	7.04	0.33	0.032
	2	12(3)	4.61	6.36	0.72	0.008
	3	10(0)	4.24	6.04	0.90	0.025
	4	27(5)	5.82	6.82	0.40	0.008
	5	8(0)	4.71	6.27	1.01	0.070
	6	12(0)	3.92	6.29	0.70	0.001

Table SI.3.14. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (TSM-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=3$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	13(0)	5.64	5.84	0.25	0.224
	2	29(6)	6.61	6.56	0.18	0.395
	3	7(0)	4.10	5.02	0.71	0.108
	4	8(0)	4.32	4.81	0.51	0.175
	5	15(0)	5.09	5.35	0.30	0.203
	6	7(1)	5.60	5.73	0.49	0.384
Pws	1	72(5)	6.61	6.59	0.09	0.447
	2	10(0)	3.38	4.52	0.65	0.024
	3	7(0)	3.81	4.65	0.69	0.117
	4	7(0)	3.81	4.58	0.67	0.136
	5	10(0)	4.09	5.09	0.62	0.057
	6	6(0)	5.87	6.24	0.55	0.280
Chs	1	41(7)	4.91	4.95	0.13	0.376
	2	7(0)	6.48	6.27	0.32	0.258
	3	9(0)	4.11	4.55	0.40	0.125
	4	6(0)	4.00	4.35	0.47	0.255
	5	5(0)	2.40	3.54	0.72	0.039
	6	7(0)	3.90	4.38	0.43	0.141
Car	1	32(8)	6.57	6.59	0.19	0.438
	2	15(0)	5.10	5.62	0.36	0.055
	3	16(0)	5.29	5.67	0.32	0.106
	4	7(0)	4.76	5.40	0.64	0.153
	5	6(0)	4.00	4.87	0.80	0.116
	6	7(0)	4.95	5.57	0.66	0.177
Gad	1	27(2)	6.40	6.64	0.27	0.194
	2	12(3)	4.61	5.44	0.62	0.088
	3	10(0)	4.24	4.92	0.70	0.160
	4	27(5)	5.82	6.27	0.30	0.058
	5	8(0)	4.71	5.23	0.77	0.291
	6	12(0)	3.92	4.90	0.61	0.036

Table SI.3.15. Testing our null hypothesis of random species assemblage with phylogenetic constraint (TSM-based). Significant results are in bold font. Random groups were generated with $w=4$ (see main text).

Food webs	Cluster k	Number of nodes*	m_k	Mean m_{k_random}	S.E. for m_{k_random}	p-value
Bar	1	13(0)	5.64	5.69	0.15	0.399
	2	29(6)	6.61	6.58	0.12	0.416
	3	7(0)	4.10	4.34	0.44	0.352
	4	8(0)	4.32	4.46	0.30	0.379
	5	15(0)	5.09	5.15	0.17	0.418
	6	7(1)	5.60	5.65	0.31	0.463
Pws	1	72(5)	6.61	6.59	0.06	0.427
	2	10(0)	3.38	3.72	0.42	0.222
	3	7(0)	3.81	4.04	0.41	0.351
	4	7(0)	3.81	4.05	0.42	0.341
	5	10(0)	4.09	4.32	0.38	0.329
	6	6(0)	5.87	5.97	0.33	0.446
Chs	1	41(7)	4.91	4.92	0.08	0.447
	2	7(0)	6.48	6.41	0.17	0.408
	3	9(0)	4.11	4.26	0.25	0.322
	4	6(0)	4.00	4.08	0.28	0.437
	5	5(0)	2.40	2.83	0.50	0.219
	6	7(0)	3.90	4.04	0.27	0.374
Car	1	32(8)	6.57	6.57	0.12	0.439
	2	15(0)	5.10	5.23	0.22	0.322
	3	16(0)	5.29	5.38	0.18	0.344
	4	7(0)	4.76	4.94	0.36	0.364
	5	6(0)	4.00	4.24	0.45	0.342
	6	7(0)	4.95	5.12	0.40	0.392
Gad	1	27(2)	6.40	6.46	0.15	0.423
	2	12(3)	4.61	4.94	0.42	0.260
	3	10(0)	4.24	4.44	0.40	0.343
	4	27(5)	5.82	5.98	0.20	0.208
	5	8(0)	4.71	4.83	0.39	0.441
	6	12(0)	3.92	4.18	0.38	0.287